

Verification and Validation Framework for Reactor Dosimetry Applications in Serpent 2 Monte Carlo Code

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ABSTRACT

The verification and validation (V&V) of the Serpent 2 Monte Carlo code for three-dimensional reactor dosimetry applications are being systematically advanced at VTT. As part of this effort, the present work develops and assesses improved methodologies for defining neutron source terms used in shielding and dosimetry calculations. Three complementary source-term strategies have been formulated. First, a geometry-independent, dosimetry-tailored fixed-source representation enables accurate reproduction of core-simulator-like assembly- or pin-level source distributions across diverse reactor configurations. Second, a generalized particle-state-based source, implemented via the MCPL format, provides a flexible and portable mechanism for storing and exchanging detailed source information between Monte Carlo simulations and associated tools. Third, an inline reconstruction approach regenerates the full multidimensional source distribution directly from a standard dosimetry-oriented source description, using it as an initial guess for a criticality calculation, thereby ensuring internal consistency within the Monte Carlo framework. Comparative analyses against established benchmark cases demonstrate excellent agreement, confirming the robustness of the proposed methodologies and their suitability for advanced reactor dosimetry studies.

Keywords: Reactor dosimetry, Fixed neutron source, Validation, Serpent

1. INTRODUCTION

Regulatory Guide 1.190 [1] defines a set of benchmark problems intended for the verification and validation (V&V) of computational tools used in reactor pressure vessel (RPV) surveillance analyses. These benchmarks include both code-to-code comparisons and experimental studies, the latter requiring precise specification of neutron sources and nuclide activities through rigorous experimental preparation, execution, and evaluation. Despite their importance, high-quality dosimetry benchmarks remain limited, a challenge consistently noted in the literature [2].

This work addresses two complementary objectives. The first is to support the ongoing V&V of the Serpent 2 Monte Carlo code [3] for realistic three-dimensional reactor dosimetry applications [4, 5]. To this end, two experimental benchmarks from the SINBAD database [6] - VENUS-3 and Balakovo-3, were selected. These benchmarks provide diverse reactor configurations and measurement conditions, enabling a comprehensive assessment of Serpent's performance in dosimetry-relevant environments. In addition to experimental validation, benchmarking has been performed against MCNP 6.3.0 [7], providing a direct code-to-code comparison with a widely used and extensively validated Monte Carlo radiation transport tool. This dual-track approach strengthens the overall V&V effort by combining experimental evidence with high-fidelity computational reference solutions.

The second objective is to introduce a systematic and dosimetry-oriented methodology for defining fixed neutron sources within Monte Carlo simulations. To support accurate dosimetry calculations, the fixed-source representation must fully characterize the neutron fission source in terms of spatial, energy, angular, and strength components. In standard practice, source terms for dosimetry calculations are typically derived from core simulators, which provide assembly- or pin-level fission rate distributions,

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power shapes, or collapsed multigroup fluxes based on nodal diffusion or simplified transport methods. These quantities must then be transferred to the Monte Carlo model through homogenization, interpolation, or mesh-based projection techniques. While widely adopted, such workflows are often geometry-dependent, simulator-specific, and sensitive to post-processing assumptions, which can introduce inconsistencies and limit reproducibility. Alternatively, experimentally derived source terms - based on activation measurements and unfolding procedures — require extensive detector deployment and data reduction, adding further complexity.

2. FIXED NEUTRON SOURCE CHARACTERIZATION

The methodology developed in this work combines Serpent’s flexible source-definition capabilities with three complementary strategies for constructing neutron source terms tailored to reactor dosimetry applications. The workflow is structured to promote consistency, reproducibility, and compatibility with both experimental benchmarks and simulation tools. Each strategy targets a different level of source-term fidelity and data availability, spanning approaches from core-simulator-style distributions to fully reconstructed particle states.

2.1. Source definition capabilities in Serpent

Serpent provides a modular framework (`src` keyword) for defining external neutron sources using built-in sampling options and user-customizable routines. Source characteristics—including spatial, energy, angular, and temporal distributions - can be specified analytically, tabulated, or derived from external data. Key features relevant to this work include:

- Energy and angular distributions: Sampling from analytical functions (e.g., Watt, Maxwellian), tabulated spectra, or user-defined distributions.
- Spatial sampling: Point, surface, volume, and region-based sampling with uniform or biased probability distributions.
- Criticality-derived sources: Converged criticality source distributions can be reused for subsequent fixed-source simulations.
- Particle-state import: Initialization of source particles from external ASCII/Binary files, enabling direct reuse of particle states from other Monte Carlo codes or prior Serpent runs.
- User-defined routines: A C-based interface for implementing custom sampling logic, including complex or geometry-dependent source definitions.

These capabilities form the foundation for the three source-term strategies developed in this study.

2.2. Strategy 1: Dosimetry-tailored fixed neutron source

The first strategy introduces a geometry-independent, dosimetry-tailored fixed-source definition capable of reproducing assembly- and pin-level source distributions consistent with core-simulator outputs. This is achieved through a dedicated implementation of the user-defined source routine (`usersrc.c`), which is integrated within the Serpent 2 source code [3], which serves as a template for implementing source distributions that cannot be represented through the standard functionality of the `src` card. The routine provides access to arguments defined by other source parameters and accepts additional inputs specified via the `si` parameter:

```
src NAME [PART]  
      [si NA ARG1 ARG2 ...]
```

NA represents the number of arguments ARG that follow, i.e., total number of parameters for source specification. For more information: 2.1.4.7 *User-defined source routine* [8].

A dedicated user-defined fixed source routine was developed to meet the specific requirements of neutron dosimetry. The source sampling is performed at two hierarchical levels: assembly and pin. The implementation supports multiple assembly geometries (Cartesian and hexagonal) and a wide range of pin-level geometries, including square, rectangular, cylindrical, hollow cylindrical, flat MTR plate,

and curved MTR plate. Several models are available to represent different energy distributions, ensuring flexibility across dosimetry applications.

All geometric information required for sampling is provided through the input arguments, making the routine fully independent of the Serpent geometry definition. This allows the source model to be tested or validated in isolation and enables optional diagnostic output in which sampled source points (position, direction, energy) can be written to external files for verification. These files are never used as input, as e.g., discrete point sources cannot preserve the high-energy tail of the fission spectrum and therefore are unsuitable for dosimetry. Instead, the routine employs semi-analytical sampling to ensure that the high-energy portion of the spectrum is represented accurately when sufficient histories are run.

The current implementation assumes isotropic emission, uniform spatial sampling within each pin, and a common energy spectrum for all pins within a node, with optional axial variation. No restrictions are imposed on assembly or pin lattice parameters. Because all modifications are confined to `usersrc.c`, the implementation uses offset vectors to position source points globally. Future improvements may replace cumulative distribution functions with rejection sampling to simplify the structure and improve readability.

A central design objective of this strategy is user-friendliness. All source parameters - geometry, weights, spectra, and normalization— are specified through the input file, and the routine automatically handles geometry interpretation, sampling logic, and spectral construction. This avoids cumbersome source-characterization workflows and ensures that users can define sophisticated, benchmark-consistent fixed sources without writing or modifying any code.

2.3. Strategy 2: Particle-state-Based Source via MCPL

The second strategy defines the fixed neutron source through a particle-state representation using the Monte Carlo Particle List (MCPL) format [9]. MCPL is an open, binary, platform-independent format designed for efficient exchange of particle phase-space data between Monte Carlo transport codes. Each record stores the full particle state—position, direction, kinetic energy, weight, time, and optional metadata—allowing the source distribution to be reproduced exactly as generated. A compact C/C++ library and Python bindings support fast I/O and straightforward integration into existing workflows.

A central feature of the MCPL ecosystem is its standardized read/write interface, or MCPL “hooks.” These allow transport codes to export particle states during a simulation or import them as an external source without user-written parsing. Hooks are available for major codes including MCNP, Geant4, OpenMC, PHITS, FLUKA, and the neutron-instrumentation tools McStas and McXtrace. Serpent provides both a dedicated MCPL hook and native MCPL support, enabling direct writing of particle states to MCPL files and reading them back as a fixed source through a dedicated input option.

In this strategy, the source term is generated by running an initial transport calculation—either in Serpent or an external code such as MCNP 6.3—and writing the resulting particle states to an MCPL file. Serpent then reads this file at the start of the fixed-source simulation and samples particles directly from the stored distribution. Because MCPL preserves the full multidimensional phase space, the imported source automatically reflects the correct spatial, angular, and energy characteristics, including anisotropies and spectral hardening that are difficult to capture analytically.

The MCPL-based approach is fully geometry independent: particle coordinates are stored in the global reference frame, so the source does not depend on assembly layout, pin geometry, or mesh structure. This makes the method robust for complex or irregular geometries and ensures consistent source representation across different modeling environments. The workflow is also highly user-friendly—no C coding, analytical source modeling, or custom sampling logic is required. Users simply generate the MCPL file and specify its path in the Serpent input; normalization and sampling are handled internally.

Because MCPL files may contain large particle populations, Serpent employs efficient sampling routines that preserve statistical properties while minimizing memory use. Optional thinning or weight-windowing can be applied during MCPL generation to reduce file size and improve sampling efficiency without compromising accuracy.

Ultimately, the MCPL-based strategy provides a high-fidelity, code-independent, and user-friendly mechanism for defining fixed sources in Serpent. It enables direct code-to-code benchmarking, ensures consistent representation of complex source distributions, and removes the need for manual source modeling or user-implemented sampling routines.

2.4. Strategy 3: Source Reconstruction, from Core-Simulator-Based to Particle-State-Based

The third strategy reconstructs the fixed neutron source directly within Serpent by initializing a criticality calculation with a dosimetry-standard-style (core-simulator-based) source description and then extracting the converged fission source as a particle-state distribution. This can be done in a single step or through a multi-stage workflow. The approach bridges traditional dosimetry source definitions - typically given as assembly- or pin-wise power, fission rates, or reaction-rate-derived source strength, and the fully resolved particle-state representation required for high-fidelity transport simulations.

The workflow begins with a simplified deterministic source distribution reflecting the available dosimetry-standard data, such as node- or pin-wise power, burnup-dependent fission fractions, or homogenized spectral assumptions. This coarse distribution is used only to initialize the Serpent criticality calculation. As the fission source converges, Serpent naturally reconstructs the full multidimensional source, capturing spatial heterogeneities, anisotropies, spectral hardening, and other transport-induced effects absent from the initial approximation.

Once the criticality source has converged, the resulting particle population is exported as a particle-state source—either via Serpent’s internal source-point output or, more robustly, through its native MCPL write capability, which records the fission source in global coordinates. The reconstructed source can then be re-imported into a fixed-source calculation, ensuring that the dosimetry simulation is driven by a physically consistent, transport-resolved source rather than an analytical approximation. Alternatively, the same run may continue seamlessly by switching from criticality mode to external fixed-source mode.

This inline reconstruction strategy offers several advantages. It eliminates the need for users to manually build detailed source models, since Serpent resolves the spatial and spectral structure during source convergence. It is compatible with arbitrary geometries—including complex assemblies, reflectors, and heterogeneous experimental setups—because the source is derived directly from the full 3-D transport solution. The method provides a natural pathway from low-resolution dosimetry inputs to high-fidelity particle-state sources, enabling consistent benchmarking against experiments and independent Monte Carlo codes.

From the user’s perspective, the workflow remains straightforward: supply the coarse source description, run a short criticality calculation to reconstruct the detailed source, and reuse the exported particle states in a fixed-source simulation. No custom coding or source-sampling logic is required, and the process relies entirely on Serpent’s native capabilities for source convergence, particle-state export, and MCPL integration.

Overall, this strategy provides a robust and user-friendly mechanism for generating high-fidelity fixed sources from dosimetry-standard inputs. It complements the first two strategies by combining the accessibility of analytical source descriptions with the accuracy of particle-state sampling, ensuring a physically consistent source term suitable for demanding dosimetry applications.

3. DOSIMETRY BENCHMARKING

To evaluate the dosimetry-tailored fixed-source capabilities implemented in Serpent, two established reactor-dosimetry benchmarks were selected: the VENUS-3 LWR-PVS experiment (1988) and the Balakovo-3 VVER-1000 ex-vessel dosimetry benchmark, both available through the SINBAD database [6]. In line with SINBAD licensing conditions, only publicly accessible abstracts are cited. These benchmarks - covering different reactor types, spectral environments, and surveillance arrangements - provide a rigorous basis for assessing the accuracy and flexibility of the three source-term strategies developed in this work.

This study validates the new features and compares the performance of the geometry-independent analytical source, the MCPL-based particle-state source, and the inline source-reconstruction method. The analysis focuses on C/E (calculated-to-experimental) reaction-rate ratios, widely regarded as the most sensitive metric for evaluating neutron-transport fidelity in dosimetry applications. Using the VENUS-3 and Balakovo-3 cases, the results illustrate how each source-term strategy reproduces measured responses and highlight their respective strengths in capturing spectral shape, spatial attenuation, and transport-induced anisotropies.

To ensure a clean one-to-one comparison, Serpent and MCNP models were constructed to be strictly equivalent—using identical nuclear data, geometry, materials, and physics options—to reproduce the benchmark configurations and perform the ex-core transport calculations. This harmonized setup ensures that any differences in dosimetry results arise solely from the source-term treatment. For clarity, statistical uncertainties are omitted from the plots; however, all simulations were run with comparable precision, supported by dedicated variance-reduction techniques in each code, keeping flux uncertainties within the same order of magnitude. This controlled approach provides a consistent basis for evaluating the fidelity and robustness of each source-term strategy.

Figure 1. Benchmarks Modelling in a Nutshell: (left) VENUS-3 PWR-PVS, (right) Balakovo-3 VVER-1000

As a remark, the VENUS-3 benchmark configuration is shown in Figure 1 (left) and the Balakovo-3 VVER-1000 benchmark in Figure 1 (right). These visualizations illustrate the basis of the transport calculations: a snapshot of the modeled geometry together with importance-map overlays that highlight the regions most influential for ex-core dosimetry responses. The importance contours also provide qualitative insight into the expected detector locations and the dominant neutron-transport pathways. All simulations were performed using the ENDF/B-VII.1 neutron-interaction library for transport and the IRDF-III dosimetry library for reaction-rate evaluations, ensuring consistency with current best-practice standards in reactor dosimetry.

3.1. VENUS-3 LWR-PVS Benchmark Experiment (1988)

The VENUS-3 LWR-PVS benchmark was designed to validate analytical and computational methods for predicting the azimuthal variation of neutron fluence in a PWR RPV [10]. Its configuration reproduces the essential spectral and spatial characteristics of a PWR surveillance environment, making it a stringent test for source-term modeling and deep-penetration neutron transport.

The results presented in Figure 2 show consistently good agreement with the experimental dosimetry data across all reactions and detector locations. Using the dosimetry-tailored fixed neutron source

(strategy 1), Serpent achieves a mean C/E ratio of 1.023 with a standard deviation of 0.006 (uncertainties based on sample standard deviations). Parallel MCNP calculations, performed under strictly equivalent modeling conditions, track Serpent within statistical uncertainties, confirming the robustness of the one-to-one comparison.

A small but systematic variation is observed between reaction groups. High-threshold reactions—such as $^{58}\text{Ni}(n,p)$, and $^{27}\text{Al}(n,\alpha)$ - yield mean C/E values of 1.029 ± 0.004 and 1.032 ± 0.027 , respectively. These reactions are primarily sensitive to the > 3 MeV fast-neutron flux tail, where minor spectral deviations can produce measurable effects. In contrast, the $^{115}\text{In}(n,n')$ reaction, which probes the intermediate-energy region ($\approx 0.25\text{--}0.5$ MeV), shows a mean C/E of 1.008 ± 0.004 , indicating excellent reproduction of the moderated portion of the spectrum.

In essence, the VENUS-3 analysis demonstrates that the dosimetry-oriented fixed neutron source (strategy 1) accurately captures both the spectral shape and spatial attenuation of the neutron field, successfully validating the implementation for LWR pressure-vessel dosimetry applications.

Figure 2. VENUS-3 PWR-PVS Benchmark (PLSA) – C/E ratios

3.2. Balakovo-3 VVER-1000 Ex-vessel Neutron Dosimetry Benchmark

The Balakovo-3 VVER-1000 benchmark was established to (1) evaluate the reliability of ex-vessel dosimetry measurement techniques, (2) provide high-quality data for full-scale 3-D validation of neutron-transport calculations, and (3) support the development of regulatory guidance for reactor-pressure-vessel ex-vessel dosimetry procedures [11]. The benchmark spans a wide transport domain—from the reactor-core center to the biological shield and from the core bottom to the top—within a 60-degree azimuthal sector, thereby probing deep-penetration transport, spectral attenuation, and spatial fluence gradients characteristic of VVER-1000 surveillance environments.

The results presented in Figure 3 show an overall good agreement with the experimental activation data across all detector types. Serpent yields a mean C/E ratio of 1.102 ± 0.014 , consistent with expectations for ex-vessel dosimetry where substantial neutron attenuation naturally leads to larger deviations than in in-vessel benchmarks. No visible improvement was observed when modeling six irradiation steps with distinct neutron sources compared to using a cycle-average source; both approaches produce comparable mean values and standard deviations for the azimuthal/axial profiles.

Slightly more pronounced discrepancies appear for $^{237}\text{Np}(n,f)$ and $^{93}\text{Nb}(n,n')$, in the azimuthal direction, and for $^{46}\text{Ti}(n,p)$ and $^{63}\text{Cu}(n,\alpha)$, axially. These reactions are sensitive to intermediate- and high-energy thresholds, making them more responsive to small spectral variations in the heavily attenuated neutron field. Nevertheless, the overall agreement remains within the expected uncertainty envelope for deep-penetration VVER-type dosimetry.

Figure 3. Balakovo-3 VVER-1000 Benchmark – C/E ratios: single-cycle vs. multi-cycle average source.

Figure 4. Balakovo-3 VVER-1000 Benchmark – C/E ratios: Serpent vs. MCNP (standard and advanced source)

Following the previous steps, a code-to-code comparison was performed against MCNP using the dedicated dosimetry-oriented source characterization applied in a strict 1:1 manner in both codes. Nearly all C/E values fall within the respective statistical uncertainties, with only a few minor outliers. The next stage involved assessing the reconstructed source, using as an initial guess the source generated in the first step for both Serpent and MCNP. This leads to a clear improvement, yielding a mean C/E of 1.066 ± 0.007 , with the effect being most visible in the azimuthal profiles. The overall trend remains consistent, particularly for reactions such as for $^{46}\text{Ti}(n,p)$ and $^{63}\text{Cu}(n,\alpha)$, as well as in the distribution of uncertainties, reflecting their sensitivity to intermediate- and high-energy thresholds.

From this point onward, the MCPL-based coupling hooks for MCNP and Serpent, together with Serpent's embedded native support, were tested using the reconstructed source from step 2. The results show perfect synchronization between the two codes, confirming the robustness and consistency of the source-term transfer and its implementation. Steps 1-3 are summarized in Figure 4.

4. CONCLUSIONS AND FUTURE WORK

This work establishes a structured framework for the verification and validation of the Serpent 2 Monte Carlo code in reactor dosimetry applications, demonstrating that the newly developed fixed-source

methodologies - analytical, particle-state-based, and inline-reconstructed - provide accurate, robust, and flexible options for high-fidelity dosimetry calculations. Benchmarking against VENUS-3 and Balakovo-3 confirms strong agreement with experimental data and consistent performance relative to MCNP, underscoring the reliability of the proposed approaches.

Future work will focus on refining the dosimetry-specific fixed-source routines to address limitations identified during benchmarking. Incorporating user feedback, their potential integration into the official Serpent release is envisaged, ensuring alignment with the code's established user-friendly syntax and broadening accessibility for the dosimetry community. In parallel, the V&V framework will be expanded to include systematic assessments of sensitivities and uncertainties, further strengthening its applicability to advanced reactor dosimetry studies.

This work establishes a verification and validation framework for applying the Serpent 2 Monte Carlo code to reactor dosimetry, supported by the development of three complementary fixed-source methodologies. The preliminary results obtained for the VENUS-3 and Balakovo-3 benchmarks demonstrate strong agreement with experimental data and consistent performance relative to MCNP, confirming the robustness and flexibility of the proposed source-characterization approaches.

Future work will focus on refining the dosimetry-specific features and methodologies related to source characterization to address limitations identified during benchmarking, as well as incorporating user feedback. Their inclusion in the official Serpent release is envisaged, ensuring alignment with the code's established user-friendly syntax and broadening accessibility for the dosimetry community. In parallel, the V&V framework will be further developed to include systematic assessments of sensitivities and uncertainties, strengthening its applicability to advanced reactor dosimetry studies and supporting continued methodological improvements.

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